

Deliverable D6.5

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Deliverable title:	Set of predicted biomarkers based on morphological phenotypic signatures in cell and tumour tissue images and their annotations	
WP No.	6	
Lead Beneficiary:	1: EMBL	
WP Title	Use case: Interoperability of large scale image data sets from different biological scales	
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WP leader:	Jan Ellenberg	1: EMBL
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	1: EMBL 11: HMGU 16: UH	

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1 Executive Summary

The imaging use-case addresses interoperability of large-scale image data sets, which is required for reusing and comparatively analyzing data sets generated by different sources.

Cellular phenotypes are good reporters of underlying cellular processes. This observation motivates the use of experimental systems such as RNAi screens or gene knock-out mice from which the molecular underpinning of cellular phenotypes can be inferred. The same information is however difficult to get for human diseases, usually requiring costly genome-wide association studies that often end up being inconclusive. Comparing cellular phenotypes of human disease samples to those of experimental systems could be a faster and cheaper alternative by allowing for transfer of information suggesting likely molecular mechanisms or biological processes affected in the human samples. This information could then be used to predict biomarkers for the corresponding diseases. However, because annotations of cellular phenotypes are made of free text descriptions that are often ambiguous, comparison of cellular phenotypes within and across domains is currently not possible.

To harmonize the annotation of cellular phenotypes, WP6 partners have developed the Cellular Microscopy Phenotype Ontology (CMPO), a species neutral ontology for describing phenotypic observations at the cellular level.

CMPO was used to annotate images from gene knock-out mice, human cancer samples and RNAi screens to try and recover preselected candidate biomarkers. Analysis of the resulting annotation data uncovered different annotation practices across RNAi screens, mouse and human samples that hamper comparisons across these imaging domains. Our observations suggest a possible reorganization of CMPO and indicate that, in addition to annotations standards, we also need standardized annotation practices.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Demonstrate the utility of the interoperability of large-scale image data sets from different biological scales (cell – tissue – organism)		X
2	Enable comparison of morphological image data of cellular phenotypes of individual genes with morphological image data of the diseased tissues in mouse and human	X	
3	Link imaging data with molecular data, including cancer genome sequences and cancer expression data		X

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

Recent advances in imaging techniques make the study of complex biological systems feasible, particularly at the cellular level, complementing existing “omics” approaches, most notably genomics and proteomics, by resolving and quantifying spatio-temporal processes with single cell resolution [1].

Correlative analysis of cellular phenotypes, linking phenotypic data specific to individual genes to morphological imaging data from diseased tissue specimens (both human and mouse tissues) could be a powerful predictor of disease biomarkers as well as drug targets. For example, when a certain cellular phenotype, like ‘mitotic delay’ or ‘multi-nucleated cells’, observed in cells after gene knockdown experiments, is also observed in cells of a cancer tissue, we may infer that the knock-downed gene is involved in the aetiology of the disease, in that specific tissue. In this way, knowledge of the functional implications of

somatic tumour mutations can thus be used to design more targeted drug therapies.

Particularly useful for this kind of analysis are data from high content screening (HCS) of biological samples. HCS is an image-based multi-parametric approach that allows the study of living cells under a broad array of conditions or under exposure to multiple substances, such as small molecules or RNA interference (RNAi) reagents that can target specific genes or processes. Resulting phenotypes may include morphological changes of a whole cell, or any of its cellular components, as well as alteration of cellular processes.

Data derived from live cell imaging is typically associated with rich metadata, including genetic information, and can be more easily interpreted and linked to underlying molecular mechanisms. As we move to higher organisms, such as mouse and human, the degree of metadata available decreases (e.g. often no genetic information is available for diseased human tissues), alongside the feasibility of assays that can be carried out in such organisms (e.g. genetic engineering is only possible in cell lines and mouse models). Taking this into consideration, it becomes evident that integrating imaging datasets from different biological domains could greatly advance our understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying specific diseases.

3.2 Biomarker prediction using image annotations

In order to demonstrate how this could be approached in practice, we used images from RNAi screens, mouse gene knock-out lines and human cancer samples. The images were annotated by WP6 partners using the cellular microscopy phenotype ontology (CMPO) developed earlier in the project to get standardized phenotypic descriptions. In the process, we had to expand CMPO with addition of new terms. Annotation of samples at the cellular level is not yet routinely done either in the mouse clinic or in the human histopathology labs therefore all images of mouse and human samples had to be manually annotated for the project and using a large set of randomly selected images was simply not feasible. To increase our chances of success, we first selected images for genes reported to be mutated in cancer and with cellular phenotypes

in the RNAi screens and for which images of orthologous genes knock-out mice were available. Due to restrictions in accessing biomedical data at FIMM (UH, partner 16), we turned to publicly available data at The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA,). Using the cBioPortal [2], we searched the TCGA archive for human cancer samples whose genetic information indicated a likely loss-of-function mutation in one of the selected genes making these genes good biomarker candidates (table 1). The question we asked is whether comparing phenotypic annotations of images would lead to the same conclusion. For this, 110 images across multiple tissues from 10 gene knock-out mice and 198 images of 34 cancer cases were annotated. These were matched to ~430 annotated images from RNAi screens.

To group phenotypically-related samples together, we first computed a measure of similarity between samples using the image annotations then performed hierarchical clustering. To compute similarities, we used a vector-based measure (cosine) and an information content-based measure (Resnik's semantic similarity). In both cases, the results were not readily interpretable. Closer examination of the clustering results suggested that samples might segregate by origin. This was made particularly evident when clustering the mice and cancer cases (figure 1) using CMPO-based semantic similarity. This observation indicated biases in the annotations.

Figure 1 Hierarchical clustering of human cases and knock-out mice using semantic similarity of phenotypic annotations

To find and eventually correct these, we investigated the annotation patterns for the three types of images looking at the number of terms used per sample, the information content of the terms used and which branch of the ontology the terms were predominantly taken from. This uncovered different annotation practices in the different domains (table 2):

- Each domain relies on a different branch of the ontology.
- The human cancer images are annotated with 2-3 times more terms than the mouse and RNAi screen images.
- The mouse images are annotated with terms that are more generic (lower information content) than those used for the human cancer and RNAi screen images.

- These observations suggest two avenues to make cross-domain annotations useful:

One is to standardize the annotation practices beyond standardizing the annotations, for example, using and comparing only annotations for phenotypes observable across all domains. Typically, this would mean

using annotations from the cellular component domain as cell processes usually are only accessible in RNAi screens.

- The second avenue concerns modification of the ontology, in particular the cell population branch. Although this branch describes more quantitative aspects of the cellular component branch, the two branches don't seem to be semantically connected. Although this could be due to the current sparseness of the ontology, this points to a possible reorganization of the ontology.

Candidate biomarkers
CA4
PIPOX
DDX41
CPA2
IDH1
EYA4
RXFP2
BAZ1A
PML
ADARB1
TRNT1
HGS
DMBT1
ARL4A

Table1: List of selected candidate biomarkers

	Terms/sample	Information content	Most used ontology branch
Human samples	5.7	8.1	Cell population
Mouse samples	1.8	7.4	Cellular component
RNAi screens	3.0	8.4	Cell process

Table 2: Indicators of different annotation practices for different sample types

4 References

- [1] Lock, J.G. and S. Stromblad, *Systems microscopy: an emerging strategy for the life sciences*. *Exp Cell Res*, 2010. **316**(8): p. 1438-44.
- [2] Cerami et al. The cBio Cancer Genomics Portal: An Open Platform for Exploring Multidimensional Cancer Genomics Data. *Cancer Discovery*. 2012 **2**; 401.

5 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

6 Adjustments made

No adjustments were made to the deliverable.

7 Background information

This deliverable relates to WP 6; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DoW) is included below.

WP 6 Title: Interoperability of large scale image data sets from different biological scales

Lead: Jan Ellenberg (EMBL)

Participants: EMBL, HMGU, UH

Work package number	WP6	Start date or starting event:	month 13	
Work package title	Interoperability of large scale image data sets from different biological scales			
Activity Type	RTD			
Participant number	1:EMBL	11:HMGU	20: CRIMMP	
Person-months per participant	37	27	16	

Objectives

This work package will demonstrate the utility of the interoperability of large scale image data sets from different biological scales (cell – tissue – organism) to enable drug target and biomarker discovery for human disease with cancer as an example. Based on the standards and services developed in WP2 and 3, we will use integrated access to systematic imaging data of disease gene

function in cultured human cells (EMBL-Heidelberg) and systematic imaging data available from tissue microarrays of diseased tissue from both human patients (FIMM, U Helsinki) and mouse models (HMGU).

This use case will thus link the four BMS ESFRI infrastructures Euro-Biolmaging (EMBL-Heidelberg), BBMRI (U Helsinki), EATRIS (U Helsinki-FIMM) and Infrafrontier (HMGU) with the standards and services provided by ELIXIR (EMBL-EBI) and require strong links to ELIXIR's molecular data resources. The comparison of morphological image data on cellular phenotypes of individual genes, with morphological image data of the diseased tissues in mouse models and human patients could create a powerful predictor of optimized biomarkers as well as drug targets in cancer. Linking these imaging data with molecular data including the cancer genome sequence and cancer expression data, will allow in silico validation of the predictions and prioritization of biomarkers for validation in clinical research.

Description of work and role of participants

Task 1.1. Implementation of interoperability standards and ontologies for reference image data sets

(Leader: U. Helsinki-FIMM, Participants: EMBL-Heidelberg, U Helsinki, EMBL-EBI, HMGU)

The first task to make integrated image data access usable is to map the (meta) data standards and ontologies present within each image data domain (cell, human and mouse tumour tissue) onto each other to enable correlative analysis. In line with the standards and services developed in WP2, 3 and where applicable respecting the secure access to medical data developed in WP4, we will implement unambiguous maps between the respective metadata. For this we will select high throughput imaging reference data sets with cancer related assays (e.g. www.mitocheck.org, www.cellmigration.org/resource/discovery/#g

enes) as well as tumour tissue and clinical data (we will make these available at: fimm.webmicroscope.net/)

Task 1.2. Prediction of novel cancer biomarkers (e.g. breast and prostate cancer) (Leader: EMBL-Heidelberg, Participants: FIMM, U Helsinki, HMGU, EMBL-EBI).

Correlative analysis of interoperable cell and tissue image datasets with their associated annotation and metadata will be mined with state of the art bioinformatic tools to predict novel biomarker candidates. In particular we will focus on genes with function in cell cycle and cell division control as well as invasive behaviour, for which comprehensive molecular and cellular datasets are available. An initial set of predicted biomarkers will then be further cross-validated against the biomolecular databases hosted by ELIXIR, drawing on cancer genome and expression data, as well as general sequence and structural properties of the identified genes to also explore their potential as drug targets